

HEALING PROPERTIES OF PLANTAIN

М.М.Ақбарова - teacher

В.Г.Мамазокирова,

Х.А.Одилжонов - female students

Andijan State University

Annotation. *This article gives you a brief overview on the healing properties of the plant.*

Keywords: *toothpaste, medicinal, chemical composition, potassium, magnesium, carotene, pectin, ascorbic acid.*

There are 3 types of plantain. 1. Lantsetsion plantain (*Plantago lanceolata*). 2. Large plantain (*Plantago major*). 3. Cotton flower (*Plantago lachnantha*).

Large plantain is a perennial plant, leafy, broadly ovate, broadly elliptical, large plantain (*lanceolate zubtutum*).

Plantain flowers are small, four-membered, colorless, collected in flower beds. The flowers of the plant are spike-shaped, long, cylindrical. Plantain fruits are egg-shaped capsules containing 8-16 seeds. Atsubin glycoside, flavonoids, polysaccharides, fiber, saponins, hydroxycinamic acids, vitamins C and K, elements potassium and magnesium, carotene, pectin, ascorbic acid. The leaves also have bitterness and tannins. Large zubtutum - a perennial herbaceous plant. Despite its beneficial properties, it is a weed. The plant is propagated by self-seeding, propagated by seeds. occurs near roads, in steppes, deserts and meadows.

The most suitable habitat for the plant is fertile soil.

Plantain leaves have expectorant and anti-inflammatory effect. The plant has a hemostatic, bacteriostatic, anti-allergic effect. Plantain is used to activate gastric secretion. The leaves are used in the treatment of the cardiovascular and nervous systems due to their sedative properties.

The healing properties of the essential oils, have long been known in ancient times. The leaves of the plant have anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, hemostatic and expectorant effect. Due to the abundance of aucubin glycosides, hydroxycinamic acids, ascorbic acid and flavonoids, plantain has a positive effect on blood clotting. The plant has a wound-healing effect, relieves pain and has a strong anti-purulent effect. Taking infusions and tinctures of plantain provides normalization of gastric secretion, so the plant is used to treat gastritis with low acidity.

Also, due to the anti-corrosive properties of zubtutum, its leaves are used in the treatment of intestinal enteritis and enterocolitis. Plantain leaves are applied to external skin lesions. The use of the plant has a strong wound healing, anti-inflammatory and hemostatic effect. Plantain tincture is used when the body temperature rises. They have a calming effect and can lower blood pressure.

Herbal extracts are used in the treatment of tachycardia and gastritis. Plantain is used as a remedy for diarrhea or parasites. Zubtutum is used to treat female and male infertility.

Taking the plant saturates a woman’s body with phytosterols, while in men it stimulates sperm production and also lowers cholesterol levels. The presence of mucus in the leaves of the plant allows it to be used in the treatment of viruses and colds. Plantain infusions and tinctures help to expel phlegm. Used in the treatment of bronchitis, bronchial asthma, pneumonia, whooping cough, tuberculosis. The antispasmodic and anti-inflammatory properties of the plant allow it to be used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract.

References

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